

Palestine and Dissent in the MENA Region

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Analysts continue to inadequately assess the impact of the Palestinian cause on broader MENA politics. There has been a great deal of focus on militia groups and the “axis of resistance,” fueled by Iranian intervention, but less attention to 1) the role that Palestine plays in dissent across the region, and 2) why the narratives of the “axis of resistance” have gained such traction in the first place.

To begin, the Palestinian question has long galvanized contentious politics in the region, and this has been noted by scholars such as Reem Abou-El-Fadl, Shibley Telhami, and others. The issue of Palestine, and the long-denied sovereignty of the Palestinian people, has facilitated the expansion of civil society across the region and spurred protest movements during moments of political openings. In my own research, I have characterized Palestine as the “gateway to dissent,” not only because activists involved in pro-Palestine advocacy begin to understand their own political agency, but also because their involvement in this work builds the skills necessary to sustain their engagement and mobilize others—often on issue areas unrelated to Palestine. Indeed, as the activists involved in the Arab Spring uprisings have noted, pro-Palestine activism helped them build the skills they later used to topple regimes.

But for many political scientists, there has been a tendency to downplay the role of the Palestinian question in broader patterns of contentious politics, or to limit the impact of Palestine to its emotional or normative impact in our discussions. Much of the discussion in the media characterizes pro-Palestine protest or sentiment as indicative of ‘Arab rage,’ most likely diffused and eventually forgotten. Some discussion also centers on the religious framing around the Palestinian question, and how it may appeal to the region’s Muslim-majority population. However, I would argue the Palestinian question and its role in regional politics goes beyond its emotional or normative impacts. This is not to suggest that emotions are not important for understanding political mobilization more broadly, as Wendy Pearlman crucially outlined in her article, “Emotions and the Microfoundations of the Arab Uprisings” (Pearlman 2013). However, the impact of Palestine on dissent should be understood in all its manifestations. In particular, concern over the Palestinian question should also be seen as quite strategic. Palestine acts as a litmus test for Arab government responsiveness.

Moreover, what happens to Palestinians has very real impacts on conditions for Arab citizens, with the constant risk of conflict spillover and the economic toll of wars in the

region. Most recently, with the new authoritarian alliances between Israel and Arab states, activists can see that what happens in Palestine is weaponized against them in their own countries. Online surveillance and repression, in the name of ‘cybersecurity,’ is one such example, as Marwa Fatafta (2013) has outlined. Thus, the Palestinian issue is not only impactful for its emotional weight, but it has very real tactical implications for anyone espousing opposition to the status quo in the region. This is why, historically, the Palestinian question has *fueled* democratic sentiment in the region. Understanding democracy and dissent in the region must then incorporate the Palestinian question.

The fact that Arab democrats have successfully been repressed in the aftermath of the Arab Spring does not change this implication, but it leads to understanding new dynamics. Today, in 2024, Arab citizens expressing opposition to the ethnic cleansing of Palestinians and the larger status quo tend to see the ‘axis of resistance’ as the only viable option. This is why, despite the extremist positions of groups like Hezbollah, the Houthis, and other Iran affiliates, the popularity of these groups has skyrocketed. This can be seen in media discourse, online discussions, and in polling data. The latest data from the Arab Opinion Index (2024), for example, shows that only 7% of Arab respondents in the region view Iran as the actor that is “most threatening” to security and stability (a decline from 13% in 2018). Furthermore, 48% of Arab respondents view Iran’s position on the latest war positively, second only to Turkey. This is compounded by the fact that the US, the global power espousing democratic values and adherence to a rules-based order, has spent a great deal of energy in the last five to six months shielding its ally from consequences on the international stage. Thus,

unsurprisingly, only 3% of respondents view the American response as positive.

Thus, in the absence of Arab democrats, and with the US largely seen as providing cover for Israel’s conduct, the latest violence in Palestine and the normalization of the “axis of resistance” will impact how people view questions of democracy and opposition. In this way, the question of Palestine is once again crucial to our understanding of dissent in the region. ♦

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